

Remote Sensing-based Analysis of NDVI Variation in Darjeeling Tea Plantations

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Abstract

This study aims to classify the land use and assess the temporal changes in NDVI in Darjeeling tea plantations. The Land use land classification was done using supervised; Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest (RF), and Maximum Likelihood Classifier (MLC), and unsupervised classification; ISO Cluster classifier. 375 sample were obtained from Google Earth Pro for the supervised classification. The data were analysed using ArcGIS Pro 3.5.2 and the classification was performed using 75% of the total sample, while the remaining 25% of the data were used for validation. This study revealed that Support Vector Machine (SVM) performed better than other classification algorithms in classification of tea plantations, achieving the highest overall accuracy (93%) and kappa coefficient (0.90). In addition, NDVI analysis from 2018 to 2024 revealed a notable spatial and temporal variability in vegetation health, with declines in certain areas from 2020 indicating vegetation stress, land-use changes, or environmental impacts. The finding from this study provides a foundation for monitoring the tea plantation health and investigated the importance of NDVI with other vegetation indices in calculating yield and assessing the plant growth to support the sustainable tea cultivation and the decision making.

Key words: *Tea Plantation, NDVI, Support Vector Machine (SVM), Validation, Precision Agriculture, Darjeeling, Trend Analysis, Land Use Land Cover (LULC), Plant Health*

1. Introduction

Tea farming is a vital part of the economy in the Darjeeling hills, where tea gardens produce the highly valued Darjeeling tea, providing livelihoods to families who are dependent on tea estates (Subba et al., 2024). However, Darjeeling tea production fluctuates due to climate disruptions such as changes in weather patterns, temperature, and rainfall, as well as ecological changes in landscape, land use patterns, and altitude, which directly affect tea cultivation by reducing plant growth and yield, increasing pest interactions, and lowering overall leaf quality (Sahu et al., 2024).

Parida et al., 2024 investigated that the application of remote sensing technology using emerging digital tools such as Google Earth Engine (GEE), ArcGIS, QGIS, and machine learning techniques for monitoring spatial-temporal changes is effective and efficient compared to field monitoring, which is laborious and time-consuming, thereby highlighting the need for an efficient alternative approach.

Further, remote sensing technologies are critical for assessing the climate variations, sustainability of the tea plantation and planning recovery efforts as they have proven to be effective in monitoring ecological changes in tea plantations, enabling the detection of land use changes, vegetation degradation, soil degradation, and pest attack (Yuan et al., 2023).

Satellite imagery indicators such as the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), Enhanced Vegetation Index (EVI), Leaf Area Index (LAI), and Soil-Adjusted Vegetation Index (SAVI) have been used in previous studies to assess temporal changes in tea plantation growth, health, and yield (Parida et al., 2024; Phan et al., 2021). However, several previous studies have emphasized the importance of NDVI in tea cultivation, as it is widely used for monitoring the vegetation health and yield of tea plants (Sahu et al., 2023). Hence, this study aims to assess the temporal changes in NDVI of tea plantations in Darjeeling over the last seven years (2024 – 2018), utilizing satellite images.

Application of such emerging digital technologies would enable the detection of temporal changes of tea cultivation and assess ecological impacts, ensuring sustainable land management and minimizing adverse effects of tea cultivation. Hence, by promoting remote sensing-based techniques, farmers' livelihoods and nation's economy can be enhanced while reducing monitoring costs and improving decision-making processes.

2. Methodology

2.1 Study Area

Fig.1: Location of study area (Sahu et al., 2023)

This study focuses on assessing the temporal changes in NDVI of tea plantations in Darjeeling over the last seven years (2024 – 2018) by using multispectral satellite imagery. Darjeeling is located in the northern part of West Bengal State in eastern India, with a geographical extent of $26^{\circ}31'$ to $27^{\circ}13'$ N and $87^{\circ}59'$ to $88^{\circ}53'$ E (Sahu et al., 2023). Satellite images from Landsat 8 and 9 (Collection 2 Level 2) were obtained from the United States Geological Survey ([USGS](#)), with a spatial resolution of 30 m. All images were processed using ArcGIS Pro 3.5.2 software. A shapefile of administrative areas for India was downloaded from the [DIVA-GIS](#) website.

Initially, two images (band 1 to band 7) were composited and mosaicked to cover the entire study area. This process was repeated for all the years. The shapefile was clipped to define the study area for further analysis. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was then calculated for the entire study area. Furthermore, the study area was classified into five classes (classes: tea, barren, vegetation, water, and built-up) using unsupervised and supervised classification in ArcGIS Pro to identify the tea cultivation area. Supervised classification was performed using different algorithms such as Support Vector Machine (SVM), Random Forest

(RF), and Maximum Likelihood Classifier (MLC), while unsupervised classification was conducted using the ISO Cluster classifier. (Lemenkova, 2021). 375 sample polygons were extracted from Google Earth Pro (Parida et al., 2024) as training sample for the supervised classification. 75% of them were used for land use classification and 25% of sample were used for the validation to identify highly accurate algorithm (Sahu et al., 2023). Classification accuracy was assessed using Overall Accuracy (OA), Producer's Accuracy (PA), User's Accuracy (UA), and the Kappa coefficient (KC), following a standard confusion matrix-based accuracy assessment method (Chomani & Pshdari, 2024; Sahu et al., 2023)

Overall Accuracy (OA): The percentage of correctly classified samples out of all reference samples.

$$OA = \frac{\text{Number of samples correctly classified}}{\text{Total number of refence samples}} \times 100$$

Producer's Accuracy (PA): Quantifies the proportion of reference samples that are correctly classified in their respective class.

$$PA = \frac{\text{Number of samples that are correctly classified in a specific class}}{\text{Total number of refence samples in the same specific class}} \times 100$$

User Accuracy (UA): probability that a sample labelled as a given class on the map belongs to that class in reference data.

$$UA = \frac{\text{Number of samples that are correctly classified in a specific class}}{\text{Total classified samples in the same specific class}} \times 100$$

Kappa coefficient (KC): Measures the agreement between the classified data and the reference data, compared to random chance.

$$KC = \frac{\text{Number of total samples} * TP - \sum(\text{All samples in each class} * TS)}{\text{Number of total samples}^2 - \sum(\text{All samples in each class} * TS)}$$

TS: Total classified samples in each class

TP: Total number of correctly classified samples in each class

The tea area was extracted from the classified image, and NDVI was calculated for the tea area only for all years. Temporal changes in NDVI were then plotted using the average NDVI.

$$NDVI = \frac{NIR+RED}{(NIR-RED)}$$

NIR = Reflectance in the Near-Infrared band RED = Reflectance in the Red band

3. Results

3.1 Land use classification

Fig.2: Results of image classification using different algorithms for 2018 using Landsat 8 data

3.2 Validation

	Class	Unsupervised	Supervised		
		ISO Cluster	SVM	MLC	RF
Producer's Accuracy	Water	0.32	0.96	0.62	0.65
	Tea	0.79	0.94	0.80	0.73
	Built-up	0.46	0.93	0.72	0.64
	Vegetation	0.63	0.87	0.54	0.44
	Barren	0.52	0.95	0.61	0.43
User's Accuracy	Water	0.60	0.96	0.73	0.54
	Tea	0.27	0.95	0.74	0.84
	Built-up	0.63	0.98	0.79	0.42
	Vegetation	0.64	0.95	0.57	0.47
	Barren	0.84	0.74	0.54	0.44
Kappa Coefficient		0.41	0.90	0.58	0.47
Overall Accuracy		0.52	0.93	0.68	0.61

Table.1. Confusion Matrix values for Classification Algorithms

3.3 Land use changes

Fig.3: Land use classification changes from 2018 to 2024

3.4 Temporal changes in NDVI

Fig.4: Results of NDVI of tea area from 2018 to 2024

Fig.5: Graph of average NDVI for tea area from 2018 to 2024

4. Discussion

The classified raster and statistical output from the confusion matrix for the classifications of the multispectral imagery by different algorithms are shown in Figure (2) and tabulated in Table (1), respectively. The confusion matrix analysis depicts that the SVM classification algorithm has a higher coefficient of agreement (kappa) of 0.90 in classifying five classes, while other classification algorithms show relatively low coefficients, with ISO Cluster at 0.41, Maximum Likelihood Classification at 0.58, and Random Forest at 0.47. Furthermore, the unsupervised classification method, ISO Cluster, produces unacceptable classification with an overall accuracy of 52%, while the SVM classifier produced high overall accuracy with 93%. In addition, considering the producer's accuracy for the reliability of the conversion from the ground truth of the classified map, SVM dominates the other three classifications with an average of 93%. SVM produced a higher chance of correct classification compared with other classifiers. However, the reliability of the results depends on the resolution of the multispectral imagery, cloud coverage, number of classes, false-colour composite, number and distribution of the training samples and random points, and visual identification of the ground truth. (G. Congalton & Green, 2010; Mitra et al., 2024).

The NDVI trend analysis (Fig. 4) shows notable spatial and temporal variability in vegetation health across the region from 2018 to 2024. In the earlier years (2018–2019), NDVI shows

relatively higher values in different areas, highlighting healthy vegetation cover. However, there is a decline from 2020 in several locations where many negative values occurred, indicating vegetation stress, cloud or snow cover, land-use changes, or land degradation. (Phan et al., 2021). In (Fig. 5), an increasing trend was observed from 2018 to 2024, while there was a strong reduction in average NDVI of 0.20. However, the overall average NDVI was relatively low compared with previous studies due to the unavailability of labelled ground samples and cloud coverage (Sahu et al., 2023).

5. Conclusion and future directions

This study demonstrates that the SVM classifier performs than other algorithms in mapping land use land cover accurately with high overall accuracy and Kappa values, while NDVI analysis showed that a significant temporal variation in vegetation health from 2018 to 2024. Despite some limitations due to cloud cover and unavailable ground truth samples, the findings provide an average baseline for monitoring tea plantation health. However, this study needs to further investigate other vegetation indices for assessing tea growth performance and yield in combination with NDVI, as well as explore the relationship between NDVI and meteorological parameters. Moreover, developing an integrated framework that combines these key indicators will support continuous monitoring and inform sustainable tea cultivation decision-making.

6. References

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